

Research article

A key to the taxa of the genus *Agrilus* Curtis, 1825 (Coleoptera: Buprestidae: Agrilinae) in Bulgaria. I

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Abstract: *Agrilus* (*Quercuagrilus*) *ziegleri* Niehuis, 2006 **syn. n.** is established as a new junior subjective synonym of *A. (Q.) relegatus* Curletti, 1990. The revision of the specimens reported as belonging to *A. (Q.) curtulus* Mulsant & Rey, 1863 from Bulgaria shows that they belong to *A. (Q.) litura* Kiesenwetter, 1857. *Agrilus (Q.) curtulus* is not distributed in Bulgaria. Key to all 10 representatives of subgenus *Quercuagrilus* in Bulgaria is presented. *Agrilus (Q.) sulcicollis* Lacordaire, 1835 is also included in the key because it is distributed on the Balkan Peninsula closest to Bulgaria in North Macedonia and Romania and it is possible to collect it in Bulgaria as well.

Keywords: Agrilinae, *Agrilus*, Balkan Peninsula, Bulgaria, Buprestidae, Coleoptera, key, *Quercuagrilus*, taxonomy

Introduction

The Bulgarian representatives of subgenus *Quercuagrilus* of the genus *Agrilus* are the subject of study in this article. Subgenus *Quercuagrilus* was defined by Alexeev (1998). It embraces 29 species (Jendek, 2026) with 11 inhabiting in Bulgaria (Sakalian, 2003). The number of *Quercuagrilus* taxa reported in the second publication needs correction and this is one of the aims of this study. The other ones are to demonstrate our opinion about synonymising of *Agrilus (Quercuagrilus) ziegleri* Niehuis, 2006 **syn. n.** and to present a key to the taxa of this subgenus in Bulgaria.

Material and methods

Specimens were collected by traditional entomological methods: collecting on leaves and branches by en-

tomological net; shaking tree branches and crowns; collecting by the different coloured tree traps; rearing of adults in laboratory conditions from infested parts of host plants.

Morphological structures illustrated in the key to species were examined with a scanning electron microscope Tescan LYRA 3. The images were produced with a secondary electron detector at high vacuum. The magnification used to take each photomicrograph is shown in the figure captions. The copyright of the Fig. 1 belongs to the State Museum of Natural History Stuttgart (Germany). The copyright of the Fig. 2 belongs to the National Museum of Natural History Smithsonian Institution (Washington, DC, USA).

The studied specimens for the key are housed in the collection of Vladimir Sakalian (Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences). All specimens of the species included in the key to the Bulgarian *Quercuagrilus*

Fig. 1. Holotype of *Agrilus zieglerei* Niehuis, 2006 from Nesebar (male). A. Dorsal view. B. Ventral view. C. Aedeagus. D. Labels. (Credits: Arnaud Faille and Aron Bellersheim).

are from this country with the exception of two specimens (one male and one female) of *Agrilus (Quercuagrilus) litura* Kiesenwetter, 1857 originated from Slovakia and eight (four male and four female) of *A. (Q.) sulcicollis* Lacordaire, 1835 – originated from Czech Republic. These specimens were kindly provided us by Vítězslav Kubáň.

Results and discussion

Taxonomy

Niehuis (2006) described *Agrilus (Quercuagrilus) zieglerei* from Bulgaria (Nesebar) based on two male specimens (holotype and one paratype). The holotype is housed in the collection of the State Museum of Natural History Stuttgart (Germany) and the paratype – in the collection of the National Museum of Natural History Smithsonian Institution (Washington, DC, USA).

Alexeev & Bílý (1980) described *Agrilus dualis* from southern Russia and Bulgaria (South Black Sea Coast). Later Curletti (1990) described subspecies *A. (Q.) dualis relegatus* from Crete Island. According to Jendek & Nakládal (2019) “The specific name *dualis* Alexeev & Bílý, 1980 is preoccupied and was replaced

by the name *alexeevi* Bellamy, 1998. However, the name *relegatus* Curletti, 1990 has a priority and therefore it becomes the valid specific name of the species”. In fact, *A. alexeevi* is a junior subjective synonym of *A. relegatus* according to these authors. After the precise study of the photographs of holotype (Fig. 1) and paratype (Fig. 2) of *A. (Q.) zieglerei* comparing to the paratype of *Agrilus dualis* Alexeev & Bílý, 1980 (from the type locality of holotype Krasnodarskij kraj: Gelendzhik) and paratype from Ropotamo (Bulgaria) (Fig. 3), both from the collection of National Museum Prague (Czech Republic) we established that *A. (Q.) zieglerei* is conspecific with *A. dualis* Alexeev & Bílý, 1980. The photographs of paratype of *A. (Q.) dualis relegatus* from type locality (Lefka Ori, Omalos) is also presented (Fig. 4). This paratype is also housed in the collection of National Museum Prague (Czech Republic). The aedeagus of *A. (Q.) relegatus* is illustrated on Fig. 15C. After all, *A. (Q.) zieglerei* **syn. n.** is a junior subjective synonym of *A. (Q.) relegatus*. According to our opinion, the reasons of this synonymising are presented below: The most important morphological characters of *A. (Q.) zieglerei* are identical with those of *A. (Q.) relegatus*. The main difference concerns the size of the species: *A. (Q.) zieglerei* is smaller with length 2.9–3.1 mm, while *A. (Q.) relegatus* is bigger with length 4.3–5.3 mm. The

Fig. 2. Paratype of *Agrilus zieglerei* Niehuis, 2006 from Nesebar (male). A. Dorsal view. B. Ventral view. C. Aedeagus. D. Labels (Credits: Eugenio H. Nearn and Robert Finn).

Fig. 3. A. Paratype of *Agrilus dualis* Alexeev & Bílý, 1980 from Gelendzhik (female). B. Paratype from Ropotamo (male). C. Labels (Gelendzhik). D. Labels (Ropotamo). (Photo: Vítězslav Kubáň).

Fig. 4. A. Paratype of *Agrilus dualis relegatus* Curletti, 1990 from Lefka Ori, Omalos (male). B. Labels. (Photo: Vítězslav Kubáň).

other difference related to the pubescence of elytra. This pubescence in the middle and apical portions of the elytra is not enough clearly visible in *A. (Q.) zieglerei* (Fig. 1A and Fig. 2A) if compared with *A. (Q.) relegatus* (Fig. 3A, B) but it is present. According to our opinion, these differences depend of variability of the specimens of *A. (Q.) relegatus*.

Notes on the distribution of some species of *Quercuagrilus* in Bulgaria

Agrilus (Quercuagrilus) curtulus Mulsant & Rey, 1863 was reported from Bulgaria by Gutowski & Lugowoj (1996), Sakalian (2003) and Jendek (2006, 2016). The distribution of this species in the country published by

Sakalian (2003) is based on specimens, which the author found in the collection of National Museum Prague (Czech Republic) and the publication of Gutowski & Lugowoj (1996). After the precise study of the specimens from the Museum as well as the specimens from Bulgaria (one specimen from Sozopol and – one from Varna) kindly provided us by Jerzy Gutowski, Vítězslav Kubáň established that they belong to *A. (Q.) litura* Kiesenwetter, 1857. Two specimens (one from Sozopol and one from Arkutino) cited by Gutowski & Lugowoj (1996) as well as one specimens from “Strandzha Mts: Papija (coll. NMP)” cited by Sakalian (2003) were not checked by Vítězslav Kubáň. The first two specimens are not available and the third one is reported wrongly by the author. Never the less in our opinion, they related to *A. (Q.) litura*. Later, Eduard Jendek (personal communication) informed us that, according to his new opinion, *A. (Q.)*

curtulus very probably has western European range and it is not distributed in Bulgaria. In his publication (Jendek, 2026) the distribution of the species in Bulgaria, Greece, Hungary and Romania is under question. According to our understanding the total number of Bulgarian representatives of *Quercuagrilus* is ten species.

According to Jendek (2016) on the Balkan Peninsula, *Agrilus (Quercuagrilus) sulcicollis* Lacordaire, 1835 is distributed in countries close to Bulgaria such as Albania, North Macedonia, Romania and Serbia. In his publication (Jendek, 2026) placed under question the distribution of the species in Albania and Serbia. According to the presented distribution it is possible this species to be collected in northern or western Bulgaria also. By this reason, *A. (Q.) sulcicollis* is included in the key to Bulgarian *Quercuagrilus* taxa (marked in brackets).

Key to the taxa of the subgenus *Quercuagrilus*

The most important characters of the subgenus *Quercuagrilus* are: marginal and submarginal carinae of pronotum coalescent (Fig. 14C); posterior border of anal ventrite concave in medial part (Fig. 5E and Fig. 11E); frons of the head with white short pubescence.

- 1 Elytra without white visible pubescence.
 - 1.1 Anterior medial pronotal lobe feebly convex; second sternite of male with two tubercles (Fig. 5D); prosternal process almost subparallel narrowed in apical parts (Fig. 5C).
 - 1.1.1 Smaller, body length 4.1–6.4 mm; microsculpture of vertex with deeper and denser punctuation; pronotum with deeper transverse wrinkles; lateral pronotal sides almost subparallel narrowed in posterior third; prehumeral pronotal carinae longer, extended to the middle of pronotum, almost straight (Fig. 5A). Antennae (Fig. 5B). Aedeagus (Fig. 5F). Body slender, subparallel, narrowed in its apical part, dark green or black. *Agrilus (Q.) angustulus* (Illiger, 1803)
 - 1.1.2 Bigger, body length 5.9–8.1 mm. Microsculpture of vertex with sparser punctuation; pronotum with slender transverse wrinkles; lateral pronotal sides arcuate, widest in anterior third; prehumeral pronotal carinae shorter, slightly incurved (Fig. 6A). Antenna (Fig. 6B). Aedeagus slightly asymmetrical (Fig. 6C). Body slender, subparallel, narrowed in its apical part, dark with bluish tinge. *Agrilus (Q.) buresi* Obenberger, 1935
 - 1.1.3 Body length 6.0–8.5 mm. Width of vertex of the head between the lower part of the eyes narrower; lateral pronotal sides widest in middle portion; prehumeral pronotal carinae shorter (Fig. 7A). Antenna (Fig. 7B). Aedeagus strongly asymmetrical (Fig. 7C). Body slender, subparallel narrowed in apical, dark with greenish tinge. [*Agrilus (Q.) sulcicollis* Lacordaire 1835]
 - 1.2 Anterior medial pronotal lobe more prominent; second ventrite of male without tubercles; prosternal process almost subparallel, narrowed in apical part or rhomboidal.
 - 1.2.1 Vertex with deeper and denser punctuation; width of the vertex of the head between the lower part of the eyes wider (Fig. 8A). Antennae (Fig. 8B); prosternal process almost subparallel, narrowed in apical part. Aedeagus (Fig. 8C). Body subparallel narrowed in its apical part, black. Length 3.4–4.9 mm. *Agrilus (Q.) obscuricollis* Kiesenwetter, 1857

Fig. 5. *Agrilus (Q.) angustulus* (Illiger, 1803). A. Vertex and pronotum (147 \times). B. Antenna (257 \times). C. Prosternal process (320 \times). D. Tubercles male (941 \times). E. Anal sternite (235 \times). F. Aedeagus (148 \times).

Fig. 6. *Agrilus (Q.) buresi* Obenberger, 1935. A. Vertex and pronotum (119 \times). B. Antenna (177 \times). C. Aedeagus (141 \times).

Fig. 7. *Agrilus (Q.) sulcicollis* Lacordaire 1835. A. Vertex and pronotum (173×). B. Antenna (233×). C. Aedeagus (177×).

Fig. 8. *Agrilus (Q.) obscuricollis* Kiesenwetter, 1857. A. Vertex and pronotum (151×). B. Antenna (251×). C. Aedeagus (137×).

- 1.2.2 Vertex with sparser punctuation; width of the vertex of the head between the lower part of the eyes narrower (Fig. 9A). Structure of male antenna (Fig. 9B) differs from that of the female (Fig. 9C). Prosternal process rhomboidal (Fig. 9D). Aedeagus (Fig. 9E). Body subcylindrical in male and subparallel in female, narrowed in its apical part, black with bluish tinge in male, black in female. Length 4.3–6.1 mm. *Agrilus (Q.) laticornis* (Illiger, 1803)
- 2 Elytra with visible white pubescence (Fig. 3A, B).
- 2.1 Prosternal process almost subparallel narrowed in apical part (Fig. 11C).
- 2.1.1 White pubescence of elytra situated in around middle (shorter hairs) and in apical parts (longer hairs). Exact disposition, dimensions and density of this pubescence vary in different specimens.
- 2.1.2 Width of the vertex of the head between the lower part of the eyes wider; microsculpture of vertex and pronotum denser; lateral pronotal sides almost subparallel, narrowed in posterior third (Fig. 10A). Structure of male antenna (Fig. 10B) differs from that of the female (Fig. 10C) and also from the following species; prosternal process with protruding sides and denser pubescence (Fig. 10D); anal

Fig. 9. *Agrilus (Q.) laticornis* (Illiger, 1803). A. Vertex and pronotum (142×). B. Antenna male (210×). C. Antenna female (304×). D. Prosternal process (174×). E. Aedeagus (148×).

sternite longitudinally depressed (Fig. 10E). Aedeagus (Fig. 10F). Body subparallel narrowed in its apical part, black or dark green. Length

4.9–7.0 mm. *Agrilus (Q.) graminis graminis* Kiesenwetter, 1857

2.1.3 Width of vertex of the head between the lower part of the eyes narrower; microsculpture of vertex and pronotum sparser; lateral sides of the pronotum arcuate (Fig. 11A). Antenna (Fig. 11B). Second

Fig. 10. *Agrilus (Q.) graminis graminis* Kiesenwetter, 1857. A. Vertex and pronotum (115×). B. Antenna male (150×). C. Antenna female (194×). D. Prosternal process (384×). E. Anal sternite (322×). F. Aedeagus (133×).

ventrite of male with two tubercles (Fig. 11D); prosternal process flat with less dens pubescence (Fig. 11C); anal ventrite regularly convex (Fig. 11E). Aedeagus (Fig. 11F). Body subparallel narrowed in its apical part, black or dark green. Length

5.1–7.2 mm. *Agrilus (Q.) hastulifer* (Ratzeburg, 1837)

2.2 Prosternal process rhomboidal (Fig. 14D).

2.2.1 White pubescence of elytra more or less dispersed concentrated mostly in apical part.

2.2.1.1 Width of the vertex of the head between the lower part of the eyes wider; vertex with denser punctuation; prehumeral pronotal carinae incurved, longer extended almost to the middle of pronotum (Fig. 12A). Antenna (Fig. 12B). White pubescence of elytra concentrated only in apical part. Aedeagus (Fig. 12C). Body widest in posterior third then narrowed apically; dark green, head and pronotum occasionally bronze. Length 5.1–7.2 mm. *Agrilus (Q.) litura* Kiesenwetter, 1857

Fig. 11. *Agrilus (Q.) hastulifer* (Ratzeburg, 1837). A. Vertex and pronotum (115 \times). B. Antenna male (150 \times). C. Prosternal process (255 \times). D. Tubercles male (634 \times). E. Anal sternite (375 \times). F. Aedeagus (155 \times).

Fig. 12. *Agrilus (Q.) litura* Kiesenwetter, 1857. A. Vertex and pronotum (115 \times). B. Antenna male (200 \times). C. Aedeagus (140 \times).

Fig. 13. *Agrilus (Q.) olivicolor* Kiesenwetter, 1857. A. Vertex and pronotum (160×). B. Antenna (238×). C. Aedeagus (153×).

Fig. 14. *Agrilus (Q.) derasofasciatus* Lacordaire, 1835. A. Vertex and pronotum. B. Antenna. C. Marginal and submarginal carinae. D. Prosternal process. E. Aedeagus.

Fig. 15. *Agrilus (Q.) relegatus* Curletti, 1990. A. Vertex and pronotum (135×). B. Antenna (273×). C. Aedeagus (208×).

- 2.2.1.2 Width of the vertex of the head between the lower part of the eyes slightly narrower; vertex with sparser punctation; prehumeral pronotal carinae very slightly incurved, shorter (Fig. 13A). Antenna (Fig. 13B). White pubescence of elytra dispersed over the entire surface, concentrated mostly in apical part, rarely concentrated in middle portion also. Aedeagus strongly asymmetrical (Fig. 13C). Body subparallel, narrowed in its apical part, black or dark green. Length 4.7–6.5 mm. *Agrilus (Q.) olivicolor* Kiesenwetter, 1857
- 2.2.2 White pubescence of elytra situated around middle and in apical portions.
- 2.2.2.1 Bigger, body length 4.9–6.0 mm. Vertex with denser punctation; pronotum widest in anterior third then slightly incurved to middle portion which is as wide as anterior third; narrowed in posterior third; prehumeral pronotal carinae incurved (Fig. 14A). Antenna (Fig. 14B). Pubescence of middle part of elytra wider, covers also lower part of anterior third. Aedeagus (Fig. 14E). Body subparallel, narrowed in its apical part. Black or dark green species. Length 4.9–6.7 mm. *Agrilus (Q.) derasofasciatus* Lacordaire, 1835
- 2.2.2.2 Smaller, body length 4.3–5.3 mm. Vertex with sparse punctation; pronotum widest in middle part; prehumeral pronotal carinae almost straight (Fig. 15A). Antenna (Fig. 15B). Pubescence of middle portion of elytra narrower. Aedeagus (Fig. 15C). Body subparallel narrowed in its apical part, black. *Agrilus (Q.) relegatus* Curletti, 1990

Balkan Peninsula and Bulgaria as a part of this region has a rich and diverse Buprestidae fauna. To clarify the species composition of jewel beetles, it is necessary to refine taxonomic studies. This article is a step in that direction.

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Conflicts of interest

No potential conflict of interest has been reported by the authors, reviewers, or subject editor.

Author' contributions

(using [CrediT](#))

Vladimir Sakalian: investigation, methodology, project administration, writing—original draft; Toshko Ljubomirov: investigation, methodology, writing—original draft; Georgi Georgiev: investigation, methodology, writing—original draft.

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